

The Influence of Biochars Derived from Different Agricultural Wastes on Water Use Efficiency and Wheat Yield in Two Contrasting Textural Soils

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ABSTRACT

A greenhouse pot experiment was conducted to investigate the impact of various types of biochars originated from agricultural biomass on wheat biological yield (BY), harvest index (HI) and water use efficiency (WUE) in two types of soils of dissimilar textural and chemical properties. Two types of soils were moderate acidic clayey loam soil (pH, 5.07) and non-acidic clay soil (pH; 7.25). The five types of biochar amendments namely, rice husk waste biochar (RHWB), hazelnut waste biochar (HWB), wheat straw waste biochar (WSWB), tea waste biochar (TWB) and mixed wood waste biochar (MWWB) were applied and their effects on water use efficiency (WUE), harvest index (HI) and biological yield (BY) of wheat evaluated. The design of experiment was completely randomized with three replications, the biochar application rates were 0% and 2%. Most of the applied biochars improved WUE, HI, and BY in moderate acidic clayey loam soil. Non-significant changes observed for non-acidic clay soil. The results implies that biochar amendments in moderate acidic clayey loam soil could modify physicochemical properties of soil and improve water use efficiency and yield of wheat. Our results further highlights that the primary textural characteristic and other physicochemical properties of soil might affect the biochars' effectiveness on water use efficiency and yield of wheat.

Keywords : biochars, harvest index, texture, water use efficiency, wheat, yield.

Introduction

Water scarcity caused by drought in agricultural lands documented as the major abiotic stresses worldwide (Hou et al., 2023). Approximately 45% of the world's arable land is exposed to frequent drought stress (Abdelraheem et al., 2019). Concurrently, global climatic change gradually exacerbates water deficits and limits its availability for irrigation in many countries (Zulfiqar et al., 2022). Considering the fast increase in the global population which is expected to reach 9.6 billion by 2050 (Yu et al., 2020), there will

be a significant threat of food shortage which particularly emphasizes the importance of increase water use efficient for crops to meet food demands of the growing global population (Ghanem et al., 2022). There is a compelling importance to develop a synergistic soil management approach to lessen current problem of water shortage in agriculture lands to meet full crop productivity potential in current and future climatic scenarios. On the other hand, majority of wheat production areas in the globe are affected by recurrent drought (Jaborova et al., 2021). Development of soil

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management practices that increase wheat productivity in the constrained climatic environment is highly encouraged (Ghazouani et al., 2023).

Biochar is a carbonaceous solid material obtained when biomass underwent thermochemical conversion in limited oxygen condition and it is often used as a soil improver to modify the quality of soils through enhancement of hydraulic properties and nutritional status of soils (Haider et al., 2020). Soil application of biochar has been alternative approach in alleviating soil drought and promising strategy of improving water use efficiency (Yu et al., 2020). Several studies have highlighted the importance of biochar on crop growth characteristics and water use efficiency (Agegnehu et al., 2017; Basak et al., 2022). Applicability of biochar in agriculture lands has reported with favourable effect on soil quality and environment (Lima et al., 2021). Biochar has positive influence on soil pH due to high liming effect of biochar caused by presence of alkaline ashes (Tusar et al., 2023). Biochar serves as source of plant nutrients and improves soil nutrient retention (Domingues et al., 2020). Biochar has also reported with considerable potential of improving soil physical properties, reducing the bulk density and favour soil aggregation, increasing the total porosity and available water content (Basak et al., 2022). The combined positive effects of biochar to soil improves the agronomical performance of soil thereby increases the productivity and water use efficiency (Lima et al., 2021).

Biochar studies in agriculture have been widely developed (Ulusal et al., 2021), effect of biochar on different aspects of soil under varying conditions has been explored (Basak et al., 2022; Ding et al., 2016). Biochar amendment to soils could be differently affected by soil textural properties (Lima et al., 2021). Biochar increases the

frequency of large pores in heavy textured soils and decreases pore dimensions in light textured soils, eventually affect water use efficiency and productivity of subsequent crops (Ghazouani et al., 2023). Some studies have also reported less responsiveness of biochars to fertile soil compared to marginalized acid soil (Crane-Droesch et al., 2013; Jay et al., 2015). On the other hand, biochar's effect on soil, is function of biochar composition, raw material characteristics, production process and biochar application rate (Tomczyk et al., 2020).

Studies addressing effect of various types of biochars produced from the same production condition on plant water use efficiency and yield parameters is considered few. Little comparative knowledge is available on biochars' effect on water use efficiency and yield parameters particularly on wheat. It might be necessary to investigate the impact of different agricultural originated biochars on wheat yield components and water use efficiency under two contrasting soils. Therefore, the main objective of present study was to investigate and compare effect of biochars originated from various agricultural waste on wheat yield components and water use efficiency under two soils of different textural characteristics..

Materials and method

Biochar production

The biochar used in this experiment was derived from five types of agricultural residue (wheat straw waste, hazelnut waste, rice husk waste, tea waste, wood residue waste). Biochars were produced in the laboratory using muffle furnace through slow pyrolysis at a temperature of 450 °C for 2 h (Mawalla and Gülser, 2023).

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Research site and experimental design

The pot experiment was carried out from November 2022 to May 2023 in the greenhouse at the faculty of Agriculture of Ondokuz Mayıs University, Samsun Türkiye. Two types of soils of different textural properties were used for the experiment. Some characteristics of soils are given in Table 1. The experiment was prepared based on completely randomized design with three replicates. Biochars were used as main treatment to examine its effects on water use efficiency and wheat yield parameters. The biochar application rates were 0% (as a control), and 2% dose. The chosen 2% dose of biochar has been reported with profound positive effects on wide range of soil quality and productivity (Busscher et al., 2010; Saffari et al., 2020; Salim, 2016; van Zwieten et al., 2010). 0.75 kg of air-dried soil was thoroughly mixed with biochar dosage then placed in pots. The soils and biochars were sieved to 4 mm sieve to have uniform mixture before placed in pots. The pots size was; 12.5 cm diameter and 11 cm height. Altındane wheat variety was grown on 25.11.2022, 10 seeds were sown in each pot, after germination were thinning up to 6 seedlings. During the experiment, the moisture losses of the pots were recorded daily and the pots were irrigated with water obtained from the rain harvest to maintain moisture content about 75% of the field capacity. The total number of pots were 36

pots, each soil type has 18 pots (5 treatments+1 control *3 replications). The experiment was concluded on 08.05.2023 after the plants matured. Plant samples were harvested from 1 cm above the soil surface, the plant samples in each pot were weighed and their above-ground yields were recorded. Water use efficiency (WUE), specifies the yield per unit of water applied, was determined with the use of the following equation (Howell et al., 1990).

$$WUE = \frac{Y}{ET_a} * 1000$$

where; WUE = Water use efficiency (G/L), Y = yield (G), ET_a = Evapotranspiration (L).

Harvest index was quantified using the following equation (Donald & Hamblin, 1976)

$$HI = \frac{GY}{BY} * 100$$

where HI is harvest index, GY is grain yield, BY is biological yield.

Data analysis

Data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and biochar treatment means were compared using the Duncan post hoc test, P < 0.05, using SPSS 21.0 software (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Correlation analyses were conducted among the parameters examined. Significant values were given with ** at 0.01 and * at 0.05 levels.

Table 1: Some properties of the soils used in the experiment

Soil	Sand (%)	Clay (%)	Silt (%)	Texture	pH	Description
Soil 1	25.3	55.5	19.21	clay	7.25	No acidic clay soil
Soil 2	39.2	35.62	25.18	Clayey loam	5.07	Moderate acidic clayey loam soil

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Results and discussion

All the applied biochars significantly improved water use efficiency in a moderate acid clayey loam soil compared to control (Table 2), the percentage increase followed the following order; hazelnut waste biochar (87.7%) > rice husk waste biochar > (55.4%) > wheat straw waste biochar (52.5%) > mixed wood waste biochar (29.4%) > tea waste biochar (13.4%). Rice husk waste biochar, wheat straw waste biochar, and mixed wood waste biochar significantly improved harvest index by 132%, 130% and 118%, respectively, compared to control (Table 2). Except tea waste biochar, other biochars improved biological yield, hazelnut waste biochar by 102%, wheat straw waste biochar and rice husk waste biochar by 57%, and mixed wood waste biochar by 32% when compared to control (Table 2). For non-acidic clay soil non-significant changes were observed for water use efficiency, harvest index and biological yield as shown in Table 2.

Analysis of data revealed that, most of the applied biochar types had significantly improved water use efficiency, harvest index, and biological yield for moderate acidic clayey loam soil but not in non-acidic clay soil. Numerous studies have reported effectiveness of biochars on improving soil hydrological properties and productivity of poor acidic soil (Ghanem et al., 2022; Yu et al., 2020). Some various agricultural

originated biochars had improved water use efficiency, harvest index and biological yield of wheat when applied in drought stressed loam soil (Haider et al 2020). Similarly, (Zulfiqar et al., 2022), reported improved water use efficiency and yield parameters of wheat upon wheat straw biochar application in limited sandy loam soil. The improved water use efficiency of wheat could be attributed to improved soil water retention characteristics caused by biochar applications successively improved wheat yield parameters (Licht & Smith, 2020). Furthermore, the improvement of soil water storage capacity due to biochar additions could sustain a better moisture level between irrigation periods, a key factor attributed to higher water use efficiency and yield of wheat (Salim, 2016) in moderate acidic clay loam soil.

Non significantly changes of water use efficiency, harvest index and biological yield for non-acidic clay soil could be greatly affected by soil texture. Effectiveness of biochar to soil with substantial clay contents is affected by proportion of small pores which already present in the clay fraction to modify water storage capacity (Lima et al., 2021), a mechanism that could attributed to insignificant changes of water use efficiency, harvest index, and biological yield for non-acidic clay soil. Furthermore, (Gao et al., 2020) revealed that biochar amendment to

Table 2: Effect of different types of biochars on water use efficiency (WUE), harvest index (HI) and biological yield (BY) in two types of soil (moderate acidic clay loam soil and non-acidic clay soil). C: control, MWWB: mixed wood waste biochar, RHWB: rice husk waste biochar, HWB: hazelnut waste biochar, WSWB: wheat straw waste biochar, TWB: tea waste biochar

Biochar Type	Moderate acidic clay loam soil			Non acidic clay soil		
	WUE (G/L)	HI (%)	BY (G)	WUE (G/L)	HI (%)	BY (G)
C	2.04 ^e	8.55 ^{bc}	5.3 ^d	4.23 ^b	24.62 ^a	12.67 ^a
MWWB	2.64 ^{cd}	18.63 ^a	7.0 ^{bc}	4.93 ^{ab}	16.33 ^a	13.00 ^a

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RHWB	3.17 ^b	19.86 ^a	8.3 ^b	5.16 ^a	22.58 ^a	14.67 ^a
HWB	3.83 ^a	16.63 ^{ab}	10.7 ^a	4.85 ^{ab}	16.98 ^a	13.67 ^a
WSWB	3.11 ^{bc}	19.65 ^a	8.3 ^b	4.79 ^{ab}	15.97 ^a	13.33 ^a
TWB	2.32 ^{de}	4.97 ^c	6.0 ^{cd}	5.06 ^{ab}	15.78 ^a	14.67 ^a

For each parameter, different letters in each column indicate significant differences (Duncan post hoc test, $P < 0.05$).

soils of less acidic properties had little effect on water use efficiency and yield due to less relevance of liming effect of biochar on non-acid soils, another reason attributed to less effect of biochars on water use efficiency and yield parameters for non-acidic clay soil

Water use efficiency appeared with good correlation with harvesting index and biological yield in moderate acidic clayey loam soil (Table 3). For non-acidic clay soil good correlation was observed between water use efficiency and biological yield but not with harvest index (Table 3). The significant stronger correlation between the water use efficiency and the yield response factors implies that applied biochars had positive effects on both water use efficiency and wheat yield parameters (Babalola et al., 2022) in moderate acidic clay loam soil. The insignificant correlation between water use efficiency and harvest index underscores the less influence of applied biochars on water

use efficiency and yield response of wheat (Babalola et al., 2022) in non-acidic clay soil.

Conclusions

In this study, all the applied biochars had a significant positive effect on water use efficiency which positively influence wheat yield in a moderate acidic clayey loam soil. Hazelnut waste biochar appeared to be more effective on improving both water use efficiency and biological yield for moderate acidic clayey loam soil. Non-significant changes of water use efficiency with biochar applications for non-acidic clay soil does suggest that water use efficiency might be affected by soil textural characteristics. Stronger correlation of water use efficiency with biological yield and harvest index for moderate acidic clayey loam indicates that applied biochars improved acidic soil properties and positively affected plant water use efficiency and wheat yield. The effect of

Table 3: Correlation coefficients of water use efficiency (WUE) with biological yield (BY) and harvest index (HI) of wheat grown in two types of soils (moderate acidic clayey loam soil and non acidic clay soil)

		Moderate acidic clayey loam soil	Non acidic clay soil
		WUE	WUE
WUE	Pearson Correlation	1	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	18	18
HI	Pearson Correlation	0.567*	-0.419
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.014	0.084
	N	18	18
BY	Pearson Correlation	0.987**	0.855**

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Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001
N	18	18

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed), **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

biochars on water use efficiency and wheat yield response was weaker for non-acidic clay soil than for moderate acidic clayey loam soil. Overall, our results enlarge our knowledge about the effect of various biochars types on water use efficiency and yield of wheat grown into types of soils of contrasting textural and chemical characteristics. The findings could be suitable to ameliorate problems of water stress in limited acid soils. A comprehensive relationship assessment of biochars with soil water retention properties is recommended to ascertain the potentiality of various biochar types on soil water storage, water use efficiency, and yield in soils of varied properties.

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